

PECULIARITIES OF GROWING CAULIFLOWER**Pirimkulova Muxabbat Khayitovna****Mamarajabov Samandarbek Faxriddinovich**

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Annotation. This article describes the peculiarities of growing cauliflower and gives a brief overview of the specific biological properties of its cultivation.

Keywords: assimilation apparatus, flowerpot, phosphate fertilizers, vitamins C, K, B1, B2, B6.

ОСОБЕННОСТИ ВЫРАЩИВАНИЯ ЦВЕТНОЙ КАПУСТЫ

Аннотация. В данной статье описаны особенности выращивания цветной капусты и дан краткий обзор специфических биологических особенностей ее выращивания.

Ключевые слова: ассимиляционный аппарат, вазон, фосфорные удобрения, витамины C, K, B1, B2, B6.

INTRADACTION

Cauliflower is an annual plant. It has short erect stems and elongated leaves. Cauliflower lasts for 15-50 days, depending on the variety and growing conditions. After that, it becomes scattered, flowers begin to appear on the branches of the head and bear seeds in the same year. Cauliflower seeds begin to germinate at a temperature of +5 C, but the optimum temperature for its germination is + It is 18 - 20 C. At + 8-12 C. the head sprouts rapidly, but at this temperature it grows slowly, the head is small, though dense. At + 15-18 C the head ended up being much larger and softer. Although it grows quickly at such high temperatures, it spreads small, at + 35-40 C the head does not bud at all, the stem extends to 45-50 cm. At + 45 C it does not form a flower. Cauliflower can withstand -2-5 frosts.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Cauliflower requires fertile soil and fertilizers. It needs nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium during growth. It is also very demanding on moisture. Lack of moisture leads to premature birth of premature heads. Cauliflower is less demanding to sunlight than cabbage. It tends to be more radiant during germination. Growing in the sun, the cabbage head turned green and dark, not white. It is unfit for consumption. In Uzbekistan, one of the earliest varieties of cauliflower, Otechestvennaya, is localized. It takes 97-113 days from seedling to germination. Cauliflower, like white cabbage, is planted instead of past crops. Cauliflower is grown in early spring and summer. The next crop is harvested in May, June, October and November. Cauliflower planted in spring should be planted in late February or early March as early as possible so that the beginning of the season does not coincide with the onset of severe heat. Late cabbage is planted in late July and early August. cm, and the seedling should be 30 cm. The thickness of the seedlings is 47 grains per hectare. Cauliflower is prone to fertilizers, especially organic fertilizers. Therefore, 20-30 tons of manure per hectare is applied with 4-5 quintals of ammonium nitrate, 5-6 quintals of superphosphate and 1-2 quintals of potassium sulfate.

Manure, potassium fertilizers and phosphate fertilizers are applied halfway before planting and the rest after.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the early stages of development of cauliflower is applied nitrogen, and after the end of the head is applied nitrogen-phosphorus fertilizers. Feeding begins 1-2 weeks after planting and is repeated two or three times every 2-3 weeks. It consists of plant care, irrigation, row spacing, and pruning. Spring cauliflower is watered 7-8 times in deep soils. In this case, the water is given at the beginning of the cabbage season and ends before the harvest. In the evening sowing, watering is carried out 8-10 times. Irrigation is carried out every 8-10 days during the growing season. Otherwise, it burns in the sun. Unpeeled cabbage heads lose their color, quality and taste, and fall out prematurely. 'must be put. The cauliflower crop is selectively cut, because its head does not run smoothly. The crop is harvested at the end of the day, when the heat returns. Cabbage head is cut along with the flower. They are placed in the boxes so that the consumable part does not touch each other as much as possible. Cauliflower is the most demanding of growing conditions among all other types of cabbage. Although it is a cold tolerant crop, it can be grown in two-year-old cabbages.

Cauliflower:

An annual vegetable. White inflorescences are consumed. It is grown in temperate climates. Cauliflower contains potassium, magnesium, calcium, manganese, iron, copper, zinc, fluorine, carotene, vitamins C, K, B1, B2, B6.

This vegetable is recommended for the prevention of cancer.

Enzymes in cauliflower help remove toxins from the body. Toxic compounds that are not removed in a timely manner can cause cell damage. This in turn causes tumors to form. Enzymes combine with the vitamins and minerals in cauliflower to enhance its anti-cancer properties.

Although cauliflower is very low in calories, it gives a feeling of nutrition, so it can be consumed without fear of obesity. Cauliflower is native to Cyprus, so it was originally called "Cyprus Cabbage". It has been consumed for 2,500 years. Cauliflower is grown in ancient Egypt and Iran. It then appears in Italy, from where cauliflower spread throughout Europe in the 16th century.

It is now used as an ingredient in soups and vegetable dishes. It can be boiled and used uncooked in salads.

CONCLUSIONS

Types of cauliflower:

Cauliflower is available in four main groups: Asian, Italian, northwestern European biennial and northern European annual plants, represented by more than a hundred varieties. In addition to white, it is also available in several other colors listed below.

- Green: Green cabbage is called broccoli. It can be found in the form of a simple cottage cheese, as well as in a prickly variant called Romanesco broccoli.
- Purple: A group of antioxidants present in purple cabbage, anthocyanins provide the color of this variety.
- Orange: Orange cauliflower is known to be very nutritious and can contain much more vitamin A than white cabbage.

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